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A comprehensive description of the circulating tumor cell: Parp2.

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The circulating tumor cell (CTC) is most likely responsible for effective metastasis (1-3). We measured total transcription in circulating tumor cells isolated from the blood of women with stage IV breast cancer to define at the molecular level the most significant changes that accompany dissemination in a migrating tumor cell population (4) and integrated these with transcriptomic study of the circulating tumor cell in humans with metastatic prostate cancer (5). We identify here Parp2 as a differentially expressed target in the circulating tumor cell in humans with cancer.

Circulating tumor cells are likely the tumor cell population that function in dissemination and do so by seeding distant organ sites. We defined the CTC transcriptome, describing the most significant changes by target and using normal blood cells from the peripheral blood as a control reference transcriptome.

Results

Figure 1: Parp2 is differentially expressed in the circulating tumor cell.

I. CTC from humans with stage IV breast cancer (peripheral blood).

n=18 normal cells from the peripheral blood (human)

n=14 circulating tumor cells; humans with stage IV breast cancer; peripheral blood

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
10038	5.00E-08	0.657	-5.4512757	-3.5828049	320	PARP2	899/21908	97.3

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in circulating tumor cells isolated from the peripheral blood of women with stage IV breast cancer and transcription in normal cells of the blood (5), we discovered differential expression of poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase 2, encoded by *Parp2* in the CTC humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of Parp2 changed more than 98% of the human transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 21,908 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of Parp2 messenger RNA in the CTC, indicating up-regulation of Parp2 disease progression and metastasis from primary tumor to CTC during the tumor life cycle.

II. CTC from humans with stage IV breast cancer (peripheral blood).

n=1 normal white blood cells from the peripheral blood (human)

n=5 circulating tumor cells; humans with metastatic prostate cancer ; peripheral blood

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
10038	2.88E-06	1.616	-4.679385	-7.563779	1.59E+03	PARP2	899/26194	96.6

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the CTC of humans with prostate cancer relative to normal white blood cells using a second microarray dataset (6) from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of Parp2 in humans with metastatic solid tumor type. (**Chart 2**). The expression of Parp2 here changed more than 95% of the human transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 26,194 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of Parp2 messenger RNA in the CTC indicating up-regulation of Parp2 disease progression and metastasis from primary tumor to CTC during the tumor life cycle.

Thus, differential and increased expression of Parp2 is a defining change of the circulating tumor cell gene expression signature in humans with metastatic breast cancer.

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Discussion

We provided evidence here that Parp2 is a molecular target of modulation in the CTC. This included a panel of cell surface markers, some of whose expression was conserved as marking the CTC in prostate cancer but of some of whose expression was specific to the circulating tumor cell in humans with metastatic breast cancer.

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Methods

We utilized GSE113890 (4) for this transcriptome study of the circulating tumor cell in humans with cancer, measuring whole transcription in CTC isolated from peripheral blood from humans with stage IV breast cancer, as compared to normal cells from the peripheral blood (along with a second dataset GSE202650 (5) studying the CTC in humans with prostate cancer for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).